

A comparison of the educational and sociological backgrounds of 19 low-publishing and 6 high-publishing rice breeders in Asia. Taken from a sample of 38 rice breeders at 27 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Characteristic	Rice breeders	
	Low publishers (19)	High publishers (6)
Highest educational attainment		
B.S. (70)	35	0
M.S. (%)	35	0
Ph.D. (%)	30	100
Source of highest degree		
Local (%)	70	33
Other Asian countries (76)	5	17
Highly developed country (70)	25 ^a	50
Av. age (yr)	40.5	43.8
Av. professional experience (yr)	12.2	15.5
Travel ^b		
Foreign travel (70)	79	83
Trips (av. no./scientist)	2.3	1.5
Preferences for scientific publication ^c		
National (%)	42	17
International (76)	10	0
Highly developed country (76)	32	83
No response (%)	16	0

^a Of six low-publishing Ph.D.'s, four were educated in highly developed nations. One scientist whose highest educational attainment was an M.S. degree had received the degree in a highly developed nation.

^b Scientists who had traveled abroad in the past 5 years.

^c When asked to name the scientific journal or publication in which they would most like to publish an article about their research results, if they could be assured of publication anywhere in the world.

They averaged slightly fewer trips abroad.

The purpose of the research was to better understand how scientific information moves among Asian rice improvement programs. The author in no way implies that the rice breeders who

published the most papers, or even papers in the most prestigious journals, are better or worse scientists than the others.

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Cult. 3885, Cult. 3948. Cult. 3965, Cult. 3964, Cult. 3868, Cult. 5996, Cult. 4295, Cult. 4078, Cult. 3904, Cult. 3900, Cult. 6001, and Cult. 3872.

The moderately resistant rices were: Cult. 3953, Cult. 3916, Cult. 3961, Cult. 3886, Cult. 5994, Cult. 6003, Cult. 3867, Cult. 6008, Cult. 3945, Cult. 3877, Cult. 3987, Cult. 4116, Cult. 13493, CR-1014, Jaya, Bala, IR5, CR-6, Cauvery, Bhavani, Pankaj, Jarnuna, IET-1991, CO2, C07, COI9, C022, GEB24, C027, C028, C023, C031, C032, C036, ADT13, ADT25, ASD4, ASD9, ASD13, ASD7, PTBI5, Tetep, Zenith, Dawn, 46-Palman, IR3273, IR1103-15-8-3, IR1614-389-3, IR579-126, IET2913, V-11/3, V-238, Cult. 2226, Cult. 1900, AC82, Thangasamba, T-336, MTU-5715, F13-22, V12, V121, T215, T1157, T347, Mottai Karu, AC-2959, Jagannath, and Malagkit Sungsong. □

Rice ragged stunt disease in India

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Ragged stunt, a new virus disease of rice, was observed at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India, in February 1978.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance of rice to sheath blight

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Rice varieties and cultures in Tamil Nadu were screened for resistance to sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. During the maximum-tillering stage, 1,404 cultivars were

inoculated with the *R. solani* pathogen by the straw bit method. Thirty-six rices were resistant and 68 moderately resistant.

The resistant rices were: ADT 22, ADT 5, CO20, Ponni, Ratna, Thillainayagam (S.AR) Cult. 55-100, V228, W449, Wase Aikoku, T1185, V42, Dular, Cult. 2100, Cult. 6547, Cult. 2210-2, Cult. 5143, Kam Ban Ngan, IR1544-340, DGWG, IR1156-501-P, Cult. 3879, Cult. 3896, Cult. 3875,

Percentage of hills infected by ragged stunt virus disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Infected hills ^a (%)
Cult. 644	89
IR30	83
Cult. 1722	83
Cult. 5202	14
IR28	73
Cult. 2361	13
Cult. 2684	69
Cauvery	64
IET2222	63
Cult. 13613	62
Cult. 658	52
IET1444	44
Cult. 1893	43
Vaigai	42
IR36	35

^aMean of 4 replications.